

Hama-cha Field Note (2024–2025): A Non-Predefined Engagement in the Cultural Sustainability of Urban Agriculture

Authors: He Yukun, Kiyoyama Yohei, Mr. Ishida (local tea farmer), He Yuzhong

Hama-cha is a type of tencha (raw material for matcha) cultivated on the sandy riverbanks of the Kizu River in Kyoto, mainly distributed across the Hamadai area of Yawata City, Kumiya Town, and Kozuya in Jōyō City. The tea gardens take advantage of the excellent drainage of sandy soils and continue to employ the traditional *oishita* (covered cultivation) method. This tea garden landscape has been recognized as part of the Japanese cultural heritage, “A Stroll through 800 Years of Japanese Tea History – Kyoto and Yamashiro.” In recent years, labor aging and persistent difficulties in tea-picking work have placed dual pressures on both the cultural and productive continuity of the gardens.

Nagare-bashi Bridge and Hama-cha Tea Gardens

Source: Tourism Information Site for Southern Kyoto (Yamashiro Area) —

<https://ochanokyoto.jp/spot/detail.php?sid=6>

This article documents the non-predefined field practice we conducted in the Hama-cha tea gardens from 2024 to 2025. The starting point was not a predetermined plan, but an incidental interview. We began by establishing informal relationships, gradually securing the conditions for on-site access, engaging with issues of labor structure and cultural transmission, and attempting to explore feasible paths of collaboration with tea farmers.

We also tested a hypothesis: whether it is possible to construct a method that enables external researchers to start from zero, enter a locally embedded and tacit knowledge site, and progressively build an acceptable relationship of contact and understanding.

I . From Informal Contact to On-Site Engagement: 2024–2025 Hama-cha Field Record

1. First Contact with Hama-cha

On June 19, 2024, I accompanied Professor Kiyoyama to Kumiyama Town, Kyoto Prefecture, to assist in an interview on the relationship between waterway facilities and agricultural spaces. This survey was part of the regional research conducted by the Japanese team of the Just Grow project.

One of the interviewees was Mr. I, a former head of the Education Section of the Kumiyama Town government. At the time, I knew little about Hama-cha, only that he was also a local farmer. During a casual conversation after the interview, I mentioned that I was researching the spatial transformation of Uji tea. Mr. I responded that he had a tea garden nearby and showed several photographs of it. I immediately expressed my interest in visiting the garden and asked if he could provide support for future research. He welcomed us to visit. Due to a tight schedule that day, we could not visit the garden in person, but the conversation initiated our first link with the Hama-cha tea gardens.

2. First Visit to the Tea Garden: “Genba Walk” and the Emergence of Issues

In mid-January 2025, Mr. I invited Professor Kiyoyama to tour the tea garden, and I joined as well, stepping into the Hama-cha tea fields of Hamadai for the first time. That day, we took a short Genba Walk (a Japanese term for an on-site walk-through to observe and understand actual operations) along the riverbank. As we walked, Mr. I explained the geographical location, distribution range, and management practices of Hama-cha. The tea gardens are located on both banks of the Kizu River, on flat terrain with sandy soil, and cultivated for tencha using the traditional oishita (covered cultivation) method.

When he introduced the harvesting methods, the conversation naturally turned to the issue of labor. Mr. I recalled that in the past, tea picking relied mainly on nearby tsumiko (seasonal tea pickers), who were contacted and organized through acquaintances. Today, however, most tsumiko are elderly, and the person who used to handle coordination is no longer active. To keep operations running, harvesting has shifted to mechanical work, usually carried out by four people, mostly Mr. I's relatives. Yet as they grow older and the

younger family members work in the city, this labor structure is increasingly unsustainable.

I began to consider whether the sustainability of urban agriculture could benefit from adopting standardized industrial procedures. Labor shortages might be alleviated by bringing in outside workers, but the timing, content, and methods of work are not transparent to outsiders. Even those willing to participate may find it difficult to identify suitable entry points. To maintain the tea garden's long-term operation, it may be necessary to establish a more standardized, process-oriented training system and work guidelines.

Mr. I invited Mr. Kiyoyama to visit the tea garden.

It was a “Genba Walk”-style on-site tour. Genba Walk (a Japanese term for an on-site walk-through to observe and understand actual operations)

3. The Birth of a Proposal: MVP and the Imagination of a “Collaboration Interface”

3.1 Initial Concept: A Draft Manual to “Start the Discussion”

On February 23, 2025, based on the January interview and field observation, I created a draft titled Hama-cha Tea-picking Process Manual (MVP Handbook Production Plan). The initial idea was for the researcher and farmers to co-create a tea-picking instructional manual for Hama-cha, providing clear operational steps to lower the entry barrier for external participants. (Borrowing the concept of the Minimum Viable Product from industrial product development, in this context the MVP refers specifically to the handbook itself, which serves as a minimal yet functional prototype of a collaborative structure.)

This proposal had two backgrounds: First, in Uji tea research, it has been difficult to enter tea-picking sites, and related knowledge is hard to access. Second, Mr. I once mentioned that the current tea-picking work relies mainly on family assistance, with young people finding it hard to participate, and the shortage of tea-picking labor has been a long-term issue. Field observation also revealed that information on work methods, timing, and required manpower has not been effectively shared, creating barriers for external participation.

At the same time, this proposal was a planned draft centered on the question of whether

to jointly produce an MVP Handbook, with the purpose of testing the possibility of collaboration. I hoped that through this plan, I could test whether it was possible to establish a cooperative relationship with the field and gain access to the actual work site.

3.2 Submission of the Draft and Initial Response

On February 23, 2025, after the *Just Grow* project's stakeholder meeting held in Uji, I handed the printed draft to Mr. I and briefly explained the idea — namely, to discuss whether we could co-create a tea-picking instructional manual. The draft noted that the content was still incomplete and would require supplementation with on-site knowledge. At that time, the draft listed the expected co-authors: myself, Mr. I, Mr. Kiyoyama, and Mr. Okuyama (unaware then that more local participants would later join).

At that moment, I hoped to confirm three points through this contact:

1. Whether he was interested in producing the tea-picking instructional manual;
2. Whether my understanding of the problem aligned with the actual experience of on-site participants;
3. Whether this draft could be accepted as a *collaboration interface*.

After browsing, Mr. I remarked, “This is not simple,” and said he would take it back for consideration, and would contact me if needed. We did not discuss further at the time, nor did we set any follow-up arrangements.

4. Early March Spring Pruning: First Observation of Field Operations

In early March 2025, Mr. Kiyoyama received a message from Mr. I, inviting us to visit the Hama-cha tea gardens to observe the spring pruning work. On the appointed morning, we arrived at the site as scheduled; besides Mr. I, another farmer, Mr. S, who co-manages the tea garden, was also present.

Since most of the tea bushes had already been pruned, Mr. I had deliberately left a small section unpruned for demonstration purposes. He briefly explained the background of spring pruning: it is usually carried out from late February to early March, with the aim of adjusting the height of the tea bushes and removing old branches so that new shoots sprout at a uniform height, thereby forming the *harvesting base* — the reference surface for subsequent tea-picking. The evenness of this surface directly affects both harvesting efficiency and tea quality.

Mr. I and Mr. S then demonstrated pruning with a powered pruning machine. During the operation, the two stood on opposite sides of the tea row: the assistant controlled the cutting height on the outer edge, while the main operator was responsible for the central cutting height, forward speed, and overall reference alignment. Each row required two passes of cutting to complete, resulting in a curved top surface. The cut branches were automatically collected and then scattered back onto the tea garden to be used as fertilizer.

5. Early June First Flush Harvest: Deep Engagement

In early June 2025, Mr. I informed Mr. Kiyoyama that the Hama-cha tea gardens were about to enter the first flush (*ichiban-cha*) harvest period, and invited us to observe the operations. We arrived as scheduled, marking our first on-site participation in the entire harvesting process.

That day's work involved mechanical harvesting of the first flush, carried out collaboratively by five people — Mr. I, Mr. S, Mr. A, Mr. B, and Mr. G. Four members operated the harvesting process, while one person handled communication with the tea factory and provided on-site support. The division of labor among the four harvesting operators was as follows:

1. Main operator (Mr. S): Controlled the harvesting height along the center of the tea bushes and the working pace. The operational reference was to align as closely as possible with the *harvesting base* formed during the spring pruning, harvesting only the newly sprouted tender shoots above it. This ensured the

quality of the *tencha* (raw material for matcha) and avoided cutting into old leaves or woody branches.

2. Assistant operator (Mr. A): Managed the harvesting height along the outer edge of the bushes and replaced the tea collection bags when full (each bag weighing about 7 kg).
3. Third operator (Mr. B): Positioned behind the assistant operator to pull the collection bag, keeping it extended to prevent it from dragging on the ground, and packed the leaves once the bag was full.
4. Fourth operator (Mr. G): Transported the tea bags to the collection point and handled tasks related to transport logistics.

The harvesting machine used was different from the spring pruning equipment — it was equipped with a blower system and a fixed bag mouth structure, specifically designed for tender leaf harvesting. The tea collection bags were sewn with mesh panels for air release, and empty bags were pre-secured to the shading frame according to experience to allow quick replacement during operations.

The entire harvesting process followed a *two-pass reciprocating* method: each tea row was first harvested along one side, then worked from the opposite direction to complete the other side, ultimately producing a curved top surface consistent with that of the spring pruning.

Factory Observation: Tencha Processing after the First Flush Harvest

The production of the first flush (*ichiban-cha*) involves two key stages: harvesting in the tea garden and *tencha* primary processing (*ichiji-sei*). Once the harvest is completed, the fresh leaves are immediately bagged and transported to a nearby factory for processing.

Because the quality of *tencha* depends heavily on freshness, harvesting and processing must be seamlessly connected. On-site support staff maintain real-time communication with the factory; when the factory reaches full capacity, harvesting operations are paused until processing capacity becomes available.

Before the processing begins, workers manually sort the fresh leaves to remove old leaves and stems, ensuring that the raw material for steaming is pure and uniform. The subsequent *tencha* primary processing consists of several representative core steps:

1. Steaming (*jōnetsu*)

The leaves are quickly steamed using a drum-type steaming machine for approximately 20 seconds. Compared to regular *sencha*, the steaming time is shorter to preserve the green color and aroma of the leaves, while stopping enzymatic activity and preventing oxidation.

2. Loose Leaf Cooling (*sancha* handling)

If the steamed leaves remain at high temperature, they deteriorate rapidly. To avoid this, the leaves are sent into an “andon” (a type of air-cooling device), where they are blown and suspended in airflow for cooling, while also being dehumidified to prevent sticking — preparing them for the drying stage.

3. Primary Drying (*hon-kansō*)

The leaves enter a brick-built hot-air drying furnace. They are first subjected to high-temperature rapid drying on the bottom level, then gradually dried more gently on higher levels to stabilize their structure and integrate aroma.

4. Stem-Leaf Separation (*tsuru-kin*) and Secondary Drying

Even after drying, moisture distribution remains uneven, particularly with higher water content in the stems. The factory uses *tsuru-kiri* to separate the leaves from the stems, after which the stems undergo a second drying process.

5. Blending (*go-ba*) and Packaging

All processed batches are blended uniformly in the *go-ba* area, then packed into large containers called *daikai*, completing the primary processing stage.

The dried leaves will be used for subsequent *tencha* refining, while the separated stems may be used as raw material for *hōjicha* (roasted tea).

At the end of the day, in a corner of the factory, we were offered a cup of freshly processed first-flush *tencha*. The deep aroma of the shading-grown leaves combined with the sweet freshness of the new shoots was the most moving moment of this observation.

II. Reflections in the Hama-cha Field: A Dynamic Exploration of Uncertain Problems and Ambiguous Pathways

The first half of this paper records, in chronological order, our practical process in the Hama-cha field. The latter half attempts to look back on these experiences from the

perspective of the researcher, proposing an analytical framework for “how to engage with uncertain problems.”

1. Ambiguous Entry and Unclear Pathways: The Dual Predicament of Non-Planned Research

In the Hama-cha field, we encountered two core challenges: the ambiguity of field entry and the uncertainty of the problem-solving pathway.

1.1 Ambiguity of Field Entry

The difficulty of the Hama-cha field did not lie in the complexity of the research topic itself, but in the fact that the entry point to knowledge remained unclear. Tea gardens, processing factories, and tea farmers together form a practical composite system that contains large amounts of tacit knowledge embedded in operational experience. Whether or not one can enter this system determines whether the research can be effectively carried out.

However, when we attempted to approach the harvesting process, observe actual operations, or establish a stable dialogue, we often encountered a certain state of standstill. From March to June—the harvesting period for first- and second-flush tea—the farmers’ work rhythm is highly concentrated and tightly interlinked. When we made requests for investigation or collaboration, we were often told, “This period may not be convenient.” This was not a rejection, but a factual expression grounded in the farmers’ value logic—production takes precedence over dialogue.

At the same time, when farmers spoke of “labor shortages” or “lack of support systems,” these often referred to institutional and resource issues rather than the organization of knowledge itself. Academic research could not directly respond to the immediate needs of the field; rather, it had to rely on field experience to achieve its own goals. This structural asymmetry left the researcher in a position of requesting access without having much to exchange.

The entry point was ambiguous not because farmers intentionally set limits, but because there was a lack of a mutually acceptable mechanism of contact. This entry was not closed, but latent within an as-yet-unbuilt exchange pathway.

1.2 Uncertainty of the Problem-Solving Pathway

In this field, the farmers were fully aware of their situation. They could clearly identify the problems of “insufficient labor” and the “unsustainable nature of harvesting.” Yet although the problems were clear, the solutions were not. Even with their experience and skills, they found it difficult to address the present challenges with existing methods.

The researcher, for their part, possessed theoretical tools and analytical methods, but without practical validation these tools could not easily be turned into effective strategies. Both sides thus had different types of knowledge, but neither could independently construct a clear path forward.

The result was that, in facing these visible yet unresolved problems, both farmers and researcher were together in a state of high uncertainty: the pathway to solution had not emerged, and existing experience offered no effective guidance.

2. Exploring the Pathway: From the “Third Question” to Minimal Collaborative Structure

In a field environment where entry was unclear and pathways undefined, we began to ask: could the researcher, by proposing a new question and a concrete action, construct a mutually acceptable collaboration mechanism, thus entering an originally closed system and co-generating possibilities with the farmers?

2.1 Third Question: Constructing a Starting Point from Divergent Goals

The researcher's and farmers' points of focus were not aligned. The researcher wished to understand local, tacit knowledge such as harvesting procedures and on-site logic, while the farmers were concerned with labor shortages and the burden of operations. This divergence in goals made research requests ineffective as exchange conditions in the farmers' eyes, leaving the knowledge entry point in a long-term state of non-response.

To break the deadlock, I proposed the idea of a “Third Question.” It is neither the researcher's academic problem nor the farmer's immediate concern, but a mediating question located between the two that both can accept. This question belongs to neither side, yet provides a reason for both to participate. It preserves structural openness, allowing each side to enter from its own perspective; and through the co-construction process, each side's concerns can be addressed to some degree.

Concretely, I proposed organizing the experiential knowledge of the Hama-cha harvesting process into a structured, visualized, and procedural Hama-cha Harvesting Handbook. This handbook could help farmers train new workers and explain processes, lowering collaboration barriers, while also providing me with a practical pathway to understand on-site logic and participate in fieldwork.

As an operational starting point distinct from both “extracting information” and “offering direct aid,” its general applicability remains to be tested. But in this case, it allowed us to approach a site that had previously seemed inaccessible.

This idea would later serve as the conceptual basis for the distributed co-creation model in Section III

2.2 MVP Handbook Production Plan: Establishing a Collaborative Starting Point through Minimal Action

“The Third Question (Interface Question)” opened a channel into the field; the next task was to establish a collaborative starting point for solving field problems.

Following the opening of the access pathway through the “Third Question,” I drafted a plan for a Hama-cha Harvesting Handbook (MVP Handbook Production Plan). My aim was to capture the farmers’ harvesting know-how in a structured, procedural, and visualized format, resulting in a practical guide usable and understandable by external participants. The plan was designed to build a minimal level of collaborative consensus without adding extra burdens on the farmers.

This MVP Handbook Production Plan was not meant to directly solve on-site problems, but to address—at low cost—the dilemma of “uncertain problem-solving pathways.” Specifically, it served two main functions:

1. Providing an open problem space that both sides could enter, allowing previously silent or scattered issues to be organized, discussed, and evaluated by multiple parties.
2. Using a minimal-scale action plan to trigger a feedback loop, so that the problem-solving pathway could gradually emerge through actual engagement and trial.

In this structure, I—as the researcher—took on the role of proposing the framework and collaboration plan, responding to the labor shortage issue; while the farmers contributed operational experience and field knowledge, responding to the research need for understanding mechanisms.

3. Still on the Road: The Hama-cha Field and the Experiment of Generating Co-Work Structures

So far, we have only taken the first step. The “Third Question” opened a pathway into the tea gardens, while the Hama-cha Harvesting Handbook (MVP Handbook Production Plan)—as a minimal collaborative structure—remains under adjustment. Many issues are still unclear, but both we and the farmers have found a starting point we can work from.

III. The Researcher as a Collaborator: Prototyping “Distributed Co-Creation” in the

Hama-cha Field

3.1 From Research Deadlock to a Shift toward Collaboration

When designing the Hama-cha Harvesting Process Handbook (MVP Handbook Production Plan), I often recalled the deadlock encountered in my previous Uji tea research. That study focused on landscape transformation and spatial structure of tea gardens. I conducted extensive map compilation and institutional analysis, yet when I attempted to bring the findings into the field and engage with tea farmers, it was difficult to obtain substantive responses.

In retrospect, the problem lay in my still framing questions and designing structures from a “researcher-centered” perspective. While these issues had academic value, they were disconnected from the farmers’ actual needs. From their standpoint, those problems did not exist. I failed to propose issues that could invite a shared response, nor did I establish effective communication interfaces or collaborative structures.

This experience prompted me to reflect: should research shift from explanatory analysis toward pathways with the potential for “collaborative generation”? Based on this thinking, I proposed the “third question” in the Hama-cha field and began to develop the MVP concept.

3.2 Distributed Co-Creation Based on the “Third Question” and the MVP Structure

The “Distributed Co-Creation” model we proposed builds on the core logic of the “third question”: creating an intermediary structure that belongs to no single party yet offers entry opportunities to multiple actors. Its core is not to pursue consensus or unified goals, but to present a concrete, actionable prototype (such as the MVP Handbook) through which different actors can, based on their own understanding, independently decide whether and how to participate.

Unlike traditional collaboration models that emphasize a “shared vision,” Distributed Co-Creation does not require agreement on goals or value systems. It is not “cooperation for the sake of consensus,” but rather engagement because each party can gain something it needs from the structure itself. This mode is particularly suited to situations where problems are still unclear and participants’ objectives differ greatly.

Concretely, the prototype provided by this model both lowers the threshold for joining collaboration and creates a broadly recognized arena “worth investing in.” Within this arena, each participant can obtain responses that fit their own needs, enabling practical collaboration while maintaining their own objectives. Distributed Co-Creation thus takes on the characteristics of decentralization, multi-point access, and asynchronous progress, emphasizing structural mutual benefit and process sustainability.

In the Hama-cha field, whether it is a researcher wishing to access and understand the on-site logic, a farmer aiming to address labor shortages and improve efficiency, or a

future cultural recorder or supporter, none need to share a clearly defined vision before acting. They only need to recognize the openness and usability of the prototype structure itself, and then find an appropriate entry path according to their own needs and perspectives. This “non-uniformity” is precisely the key premise for Distributed Co-Creation to function in practice.

3.3 Collaboration Is Not “Entering the Other” (Participant Observation) : Repositioning the Researcher

In the Hama-cha field, I gradually realized that entering the field requires shedding the “researcher-centered vantage point.” What we face is not an object waiting for interpretation or support, but a knowledge system operating according to its own internal logic. In this system, the researcher can neither dominate nor direct everything, but is merely one of many possible points of inclusion.

IV. Reflections on the Cultural Sustainability of Urban Agriculture

Through the Hama-cha field process, we gradually realized that the sustainability of urban agricultural culture partly depends on its ability to form connections with new actors and new problem-awareness. The vitality of a culture may, in fact, reside in these specific new connections.

Whether the MVP handbook developed in the Hama-cha practice will be accepted and continue to evolve remains uncertain. We will continue to advance the project and record the process.

Terminology Note

In this project:

Minimum Viable Product (MVP) — the theoretical framework for building a basic yet functional collaborative structure.

MVP Handbook — the final co-created field deliverable, which has not yet been produced.

MVP Handbook Production Plan — the current output at this stage, a roadmap for developing the handbook.

Throughout this paper, “MVP” refers only to the theoretical framework, “MVP Handbook” to the final deliverable, and “MVP Handbook Production Plan” to the current stage output.

Collaborators and Acknowledgments

This research and practice were carried out in collaboration with the Hama-cha Co-Creation Team, whose members include HE YUKUN, Mr. Ishida, Mr. Kiyoyama Yohei and Ms. Okuyama Yukiho.

We sincerely thank the Hama-Cha Collaborators—Mr. Ishida, Mr. S, Mr. A, Mr. B, and Mr. G—for their generous support in fieldwork, knowledge sharing, and on-site assistance. Their situated knowledge and practical experience constitute an essential part of this article. (Mr. Ishida serves as both a team member and a collaborating farmer.)

We are deeply grateful to Professor Kanki Kiyoko of the Department of Architecture, Kyoto University, for her guidance in research design and theoretical development, as well as to all community members and partners who contributed through observations, interviews, and the provision of materials.

We also wish to express our special thanks to the international collaborative research project Just Grow for its support. In particular, we thank Dr. Rose and Professor Patrick for their inspiration regarding research frameworks and co-creation concepts. We further acknowledge the active participation of Just Grow project members in various Zoom meetings; their presentations and discussions at SRI2023, SRI2024, and the Stockholm stakeholder meeting provided valuable insights and significant inspiration for the development of this study's research design and practical approaches.

In addition, I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my brother, HE YUZHONG, who provided significant inspiration and encouragement for the concept of this study through his practical experience in "Zero-Budget Gemba DX," and who was also involved in the conceptual review and partial writing of this paper.

All on-site content, personal names, and related images cited in this paper have been used with the permission of the individuals concerned.

Postscript

The frameworks and perspectives discussed in the latter half of this paper are all provisional constructs that I am currently developing through ongoing experimentation within the Hama-cha project, grounded in my own field experiences. Accordingly, the

reflections presented here do not represent definitive conclusions; they remain subject to change and further refinement as the project evolves and new forms of collaboration emerge.

I warmly welcome opportunities for dialogue and discussion with those who share an interest in these ideas and ongoing attempts.

This paper is part of the international joint research project “JST–Belmont Forum: JUST GROW – Co-designing justice-centric indicators and governance principles to intensify urban agriculture sustainably and equitably.”